

Supplementary File 2. Search strategy for literature databases and clinical trial registries

Database: Ichushi-Web

Date of search: September 16, 2025

#	Search terms	Hits
#1	Lycopene/TH or リコピン/AL or Lycopene/AL or リコペン/AL or ψ-カロテン/AL or プサイカロテン/AL or psiカロテン/AL or ψ-Carotene/AL or psi-Carotene/AL or LYC-O-MATO/AL or LYCOMATO/AL or "LYC O MATO"/AL or ATERONON/AL or "BLAKESLEA TRISPORA"/AL or "CI 75125"/AL or CI-75125/AL or CI75125/AL or "E 160D"/AL or E-160D/AL or E160D/AL or LYCORED/AL or "MEXORYL SAQ"/AL or MEXORYL-SAQ/AL or "NSC 407322"/AL or NSC-407322/AL or NSC407322/AL or REDIVIVO/AL or SOLANORUBIN/AL or "TOMAT O RED"/AL or TOMAT-O-RED/AL or 502-65-8/AL or 13018-46-7/AL or トマト/TH or トマト/TA or "Lycopersicon esculentum"/AL or "Solanum lycopersicum"/AL or Tomato/TA or 赤茄子/AL or アカナス/AL or あかなす/AL or 蕃茄/AL or 唐柿/AL or 小金瓜/AL or コガネウリ/AL or 珊瑚樹茄子/AL or さんごじゅなす/AL or サンゴジュナス/AL or スイカ属/TH or スイカ/TA or Citrullus/AL or "Water Melon"/TA or Watermelon/TA or 西瓜/AL	2,373
#2	血管内皮/TH or 血管内皮/AL or "vascular endotheli"/AL or "vessel endotheli"/AL or 脈管内皮/AL or 脈内皮/AL or 内皮機能/AL or "Capillary Endotheli"/AL or "endothel funct"/AL or "endothel dysfunc"/AL or (血管/TH or 内皮/TH or 血管/AL or 脈管/AL or 脈内/AL or Blood/AL or Vessel/AL or Vascul/AL or Vein/AL or Endothel/AL)	1,241,354
#3	FMD/AL or "Flow-mediated Dilation"/AL or "Flow mediated Dilation"/AL or "Flow-mediated Vasodilation"/AL or "Flow mediated Vasodilation"/AL or "血流依存性血管拡張反応"/AL or "内皮依存性血管拡張反応"/AL	1,790
#4	RH-PAT/AL or RHPAT/AL or "reactive hyperemia peripheral arterial tonometry"/AL or "Reactive Hyperemia-Peripheral Arterial Tonometry"/AL or 反応性充血末梢動脈トノメトリー/AL or 反応性充血末梢動脈圧力測定/AL or 末梢動脈トノメトリー/AL or 末梢動脈圧力測定/AL	115
#5	プレチスモグラフィー/TH or Plethysmograph/AL or プレスチモグラフ/AL or プレチスモグラフ/AL or プレシスモグラフ/AL or 容積脈波/AL or 体積記録/AL or 体積変動記録/AL	4,593
#6	#2 or #3 or #4 or #5	1,244,804
#7	#1 and #6 and PT=原著論文,総説	105

Database: MEDLINE (PubMed)

Date of search: September 16, 2025

#	Search terms	Hits
#1	"lycopene"[Supplementary Concept] OR "lycopene"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopene*"[All Fields]	7,282
#2	"solanum lycopersicum"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopersicon esculentum"[All Fields] OR "tomato*"[All Fields] OR "watermelon*"[All Fields] OR "water melon*"[All Fields]	42,275
#3	#1 OR #2	47,445
#4	"randomized controlled trial"[Publication Type] OR "controlled clinical trial"[Publication Type] OR "randomized"[Title/Abstract] OR "placebo"[Title/Abstract] OR "clinical trials as topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR "randomly"[Title/Abstract] OR "trial"[Title]	1,730,389
#5	"case control studies"[MeSH Terms] OR "control groups"[MeSH Terms] OR ("case*"[Title/Abstract] AND "control*"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("case*"[Title/Abstract] AND "comparison*"[Title/Abstract]) OR "control group*"[Title/Abstract] OR "cohort studies"[MeSH Terms] OR "cohort"[Title/Abstract] OR "longitudinal"[Title/Abstract] OR "prospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "retrospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "cross sectional studies"[MeSH Terms] OR "cross-sectional"[Title/Abstract] OR "transversal stud*"[Title/Abstract]	5,595,922
#6	#4 OR #5	6,707,141
#7	#6 NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms])	6,348,789
#8	#3 AND #7	3,323
#9	"vascular "[Title/Abstract] OR "endotheli*"[Title/Abstract] OR "blood vessel*"[All Fields] OR "blood vessels"[MeSH Terms] OR "flow mediated dilatation"[All Fields] OR "plethysmograph "[All Fields] OR "RH-PAT"[All Fields] OR "peripheral arterial tonometry" [All Fields]	1,614,559
#10	#8 AND #9	174

Database: Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials(The Cochrane Library/Wiley)

Date of search: September 16, 2025

#	Search terms	Hits
#1	(lycopene* OR Prolycopene OR Pro-Lycopene OR Pro Lycopene OR LYC-O-MATO OR LYCOMATO OR LYC O MATO OR All-trans-Lycopene):ti,ab,kw	768
#2	MeSH descriptor: [Lycopene] explode all trees	303
#3	MeSH descriptor: [Solanum lycopersicum] explode all trees	144
#4	(tomato OR tomatoes OR solanum lycopersicum OR lycopersicon esculentum OR watermelon OR water melon):ti,ab,kw	847
#5	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4	1,369
#6	MeSH descriptor: [Blood Vessels] explode all trees	18,605
#7	(vascular OR endotheli* OR blood vessel* OR flow mediated dilatation OR plethysmograph OR RH-PAT OR peripheral arterial tonometry):ti,ab,kw	77,803
#8	#6 OR #7	86,553
#9	#5 AND #8 in Trials	119

Database: Global Index Medicus

Date of search: September 16, 2025

#	Search terms	Hits
#1	((lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") OR (mh:"lycopene")) AND (((random* OR trial* OR placebo OR cohort OR case-control* OR cross-section*)) OR (mh:("Clinical Study" OR "Clinical Trial" OR "Randomized Controlled Trial" OR "Controlled Clinical Trial" OR "Epidemiologic Studies" OR "Case-Control Studies" OR "Cohort Studies" OR "Cross-Sectional Studies"))))	94

Database: ICTRP

Date of search: September 16, 2025

#	Search terms	Hits
#1	(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Title :Recruitment status is ALL	118 records for 116 trials
#2	(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Intervention :Recruitment status is ALL	144 records for 142 trials
	Number of records after deduplication	144 records for 142 trials

Database: ClinicalTrials.gov

Date of search: September 16, 2025

#	Search terms	Hits
#1	(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Other terms	125
#2	(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Intervention/treatmen	89
	Number of records after deduplication	125

Database: UMIN-CTR

Date of search: September 16, 2025

#	Search terms	Hits
#1	リコピン	20
#2	リコペン	8
#3	プロリコピン	0
#4	ライコマート	0
#5	lycopene	25
#6	prolycopene	0
#7	LYC-O-MATO	0
#8	All-trans-lycopene	0
	Number of records after deduplication	29